

Performance Appraisal and Employee Performance: A Meta-Analysis from the Perspective of Goal Theory

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 06 February 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Performance appraisal and employee Performance Goal theory Meta-analysis Employee performance</p>	<p>This paper sought to investigate the assumption of the Goal theory in the context of performance appraisal and employee performance. The Goal theory assumes that setting of goals and appraisal of the goals are associated with higher motivation, commitment and goal-achievement. The paper used meta-analytic approach to examine the existing literature on the assumption of the Goal theory, specifically in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. The meta-analytic results from 27 studies indicated that the assumption of the Goal theory holds in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. That is, performance appraisal is positively correlated with employee performance. However, the study found that the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance is influenced by the moderating effects of the sector (public vs private) where the study is conducted, organizational size (large vs small), sampling technique (probability vs non-probability) and the sample type (cross-sectional vs longitudinal). The study found that these moderators cause inconsistencies in the existing findings on the assumption of the Goal theory in the appraisal-performance nexus. The study therefore proposed a revised Goal theory framework in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Moreover, the study established that organizations need to be cautious when using the Goal theory, by first identifying the factors that could influence, moderate or limit its application. Equally, researchers need to be careful about the moderating factors when employing the theoretical framework of the Goal theory in their studies, to avoid presenting inaccurate findings on the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.</p>

1. Introduction

Since the development of performance appraisal studies in the early 1930s, several studies have been conducted on the influence of performance appraisal on employee performance. However, different studies on the topic have shown different findings and this has created a debate about the nature of the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Some of the studies show that performance appraisal is positively correlated with employee performance (Chaponda, 2014; Nganga, Wanjiku & Sakwa, 2013). These studies are in agreement with the established theories of performance appraisal such as the Goal Theory. Other studies have found that performance appraisal is negatively correlated with employee performance (Ahmad et al., 2014; Attipoe, Agordzo & Seddoh, 2021). Some researchers have even found that performance appraisal has zero and statistically insignificant influence on employee performance (Jansen, 2016; Alvi, Surani & Hirani (2013). These contradictory results arise from lack of systematization of the current literature on the influence of performance appraisal on employee performance, as described by the Goal theory. The divergence of the existing studies creates confusion about the assumption of the Goal theory and has made it difficult to draw conclusions about the strength and direction of the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

This paper therefore utilized meta-analytic approach to systematize the existing literature on the assumption of the Goal theory, specifically in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. The use of meta-analysis is preferred over the standard narrative literature review because it allows researchers to quantitatively compare the estimates obtained from the different studies (Weichselbaumer & WinterEbmer, 2005). By using a standardized method to compare the estimates, meta-analysis reduces the problem of bias that is common in narrative literature review (Neyeloff, Fuchs & Moreira, 2012).

The paper is divided into ten parts. Part I consists of the introduction. Part II consists of the literature review of performance appraisal, employee

performance, the Goal theory and sample conflicting studies on performance appraisal and employee performance. Part III consists of the meta-analysis technique used in this study. Part IV consists of selection criteria of the studies used in this research. Part V consists of coding and data extraction to identify performance outcomes and the potential moderating factors in the assumption of the Goal theory. Part VI consists of the findings. Part VII consists of discussion of the findings. Part VIII consists of the conclusions about the findings. Part IX consists of the limitations of the study while Part X consists of the recommendations for future studies.

2. Literature review

2.1 Performance appraisal and employee performance

The term “performance appraisal” is often used interchangeably with performance evaluation, assessment, and performance review or employee appraisal. The term refers to the different methods and processes used by organizations to evaluate the level of performance of their employees. Performance appraisal is a common human resource management practice that is used to identify the strengths and weaknesses of employees in order to improve organizational performance (Abdullah et al., 2021). In many organizations, performance appraisal is based on predetermined performance indicators that the organizations assess if employees have met during the period of appraisal. In general, performance appraisal involves establishing goals, communicating performance expectations, measuring actual performance, comparing the performance with the set standards, discussing the performance with the employees and initiating corrective actions (Katerina, Andrea & Gabriela, 2013). Other than evaluating the individual and organizational performance, performance appraisal identifies whether employees possess the desired core competencies needed for their responsibilities (Sumaira & Muhammad, 2017). Moreover, performance appraisal aims to improve the relationship between employees and management, and activates decision making regarding necessary changes for the employees and the

organization (Cintron & Flaniken, 2019). According to Dijk (2015), evaluating employees is important because their knowledge, skills and competencies are the most valuable resources an organization can have in modern competitive environments.

On the other hand, employee performance is the extent to which employees execute the required tasks in order to fulfill their job duties. According to Rabindra & Lalatendu (2017), performance is the set of behaviors, actions and outcomes of employees that contribute to achievement of organizational goals. Employee performance is a multicomponent concept comprising of dimensions such as quality of work, accuracy, productivity level, job knowledge, problem solving and ability to work with others. Researchers have identified multiple performance outcomes and indicators. For instance, Griffin et al. (2007) identify task proficiency, task adaptability and task proactivity as the important aspects of employee performance. Audrey & Patrice (2012) found that aspects of performance include creativity, reactivity, interpersonal adaptableness and management of work-related stress. In other words, employee performance is not about task performance only, but also contextual and adaptive performance within the organizations (Rabindra & Lalatendu, 2017).

Performance appraisal and employee performance are two concepts that cannot be in isolation of the other. Performance appraisal reviews the employee performance in the organizations. Performance appraisal processes seek to enhance employee performance through high productivity, increased morale and mutual interaction between the supervisors and subordinates in an organization. Employee performance is a factor that cannot be left in anticipation that it develops naturally among the employees. It has to be facilitated, cultivated and accommodated by some form of appraisal within an organization (Kihama & Wainaina, 2019). The appraisals could take many forms such as 360-Degree Appraisal, Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scale (BARS), Straight-Ranking Appraisals and Forced Distribution Appraisals. In general, performance appraisal aims to provide the basis for developing capabilities for improving the current and future performance of the employees.

2.2 The Goal theory in the context of performance appraisal and employee performance

The goal theory was developed by Nicholls (1984). This theory states that goal setting and evaluation are associated with higher motivation, commitment and goal-achievement. The theory posits that specific and challenging goals along with appropriate feedback mechanism contribute to better and improved task performance. According to the theory, a link

exists between goals, performance evaluation and the effort employees put in place to achieve the goals. In the context of performance appraisal, the Goal theory emphasizes the role of evaluating employees' output in an organization. The theory provides a framework for improving employee performance not only by increasing motivational efforts, but also improving the feedback quality through appraisals and engagements. Latham and Locke (2007) pointed out that in the field of human resource management, setting and appraisal of goals has a positive impact on employees' performance.

2.3 Sample conflicting empirical studies on the assumption of the Goal theory in the context of performance appraisal and employee performance.

There are inconsistencies that exist in the current literature on the assumption of Goal theory in the context of performance appraisal and employee performance. The current studies have indicated mixed findings on the nature, strength and direction of the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Different studies have found weak and strong positive correlations, weak and strong negative correlations and even statistically insignificant relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

2.3.1 Studies showing positive and statistically significant correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance.

Chaponda (2014) adopted a descriptive research design to investigate the link between performance appraisal and organizational performance in non-governmental organizations. The study utilized a sample of 171 respondents selected using stratified sampling. The findings revealed that performance appraisal system improves job performance and leads to employee motivation and productivity. The correlation coefficient ($r=0.36$, $p<0.01$) indicated a positive correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance. Another study by Nganga, Wanjiku & Sakwa (2013) utilized explanatory research design to examine the relationship between performance appraisal and firm performance in the Kenya's agricultural sector. A sample of 142 Human Resource Officers was randomly picked for the study. The Pearson correlation coefficient between performance appraisal and firm performance appraisal ($r=0.480$, $p<0.05$) indicated that there is a positive linear relationship between performance appraisal and firm performance.

Ayomikum (2017) sought to evaluate the effectiveness of performance appraisal systems on employee motivation. The study adopted mixed research designs and Survey Method obtained a sample of 45 respondents. The correlation model indicated a significant positive outcome when the organizations use performance appraisal tool to motivate its employees ($r=0.466$, $p<0.05$). The study also found that if an organization uses more than one appraisal technique, then the satisfaction of employees increases which consequently lead to higher motivational levels and performance. In a similar study, Ndago (2020) assessed the link between performance appraisal and productivity of employee in state correctional centers in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive research design and a sample size of 116 respondents. Primary data was obtained using structured questionnaires and analyzed descriptively and inferentially. The correlation findings revealed a positive relationship between employee evaluation and employee productivity ($r=0.6477$, $p<0.05$).

Kumari (2015) on the other hand, investigated the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance in India's telecom sector. The study employed standardized questionnaires to collect data from 80 respondents. The correlation results showed that there exists a positive correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance. The regression analysis further indicated there is a statistically significant impact of performance appraisal on employee performance. In addition, Moraa & Datche (2019) assessed the link between performance appraisal and employee performance in the National Insurance Fund in Kenya. The sample of the study comprised of 306 individuals and data was collected using structured questionnaires. The study established that there is a positive linear relationship between performance review and employee performance.

Weerakkodi & Mahalekange (2013) investigated the relationship between performance appraisal on employee outcomes. The study used structured questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 110 samples that were obtained by simple random sampling. The collected data was analysed through correlations of the study variables and regression in order to answer the hypotheses of the study. The results indicated that there exists a weak but positive relationship between performance appraisal,

satisfaction and employee outcomes. [Sopia \(2016\)](#) however, utilized secondary data from to evaluate the link between performance appraisal and job performance. The study found a positive correlation trend between performance appraisal and job performance based on both the theoretical and empirical studies. According to the study, if performance appraisal carried out properly, it can help improve performance by identifying the strengths and weaknesses on the employees.

2.3.2 Studies showing negative and statistically significant correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance.

A comparative study by [Ahmad et al. \(2014\)](#) examined the relationship between banking industry based appraisal and rewards system and their effects on employee performance. The study utilized structured questionnaires to obtain data from a sample of 225 respondents drawn from banking institutions. The findings revealed that performance appraisal is negatively correlated with employee performance ($r = -0.27, p < 0.05$). The predicting value of regression results ($\beta = -0.28, t = -3.612$) indicated that performance appraisals negatively affect employee performance. In another study, [Naseed et al. \(2019\)](#) examined the effect of performance appraisal on work outcomes. A sample of 100 was selected using convenient sampling technique and data was collected from the respondents using structured questionnaires. The study found that performance appraisal is negatively correlated with work outcomes of the employees and reduces their job satisfaction ($r = -0.676, p < 0.05$).

[Attipoe, Agordzo & Seddoh \(2021\)](#) investigated the influence of performance appraisal system on productivity of employees in selected public senior high schools in Ghana. The study utilized a sample of 108 respondents selected using both probability and nonprobability sampling methods. Information from the respondents was collected using structured questionnaires. The collected data was analysed descriptively and by correlation method. The findings indicated a negative relationship between performance appraisal and productivity of the employees. [Patrick \(2014\)](#) further analysed performance appraisal and job satisfaction. The study obtained data from longitudinal sample 12,000 respondents. The findings revealed that performance appraisal is negatively correlated with satisfaction and performance, more so if it is not linked to monetary outcomes ($r = -0.03, p < 0.01$).

[Rahahleh, Alabaddi & Moflih \(2019\)](#) investigated the influence of performance appraisal on the performance of employees in the banks operating in southern Jordan. The study collected data through closed ended structured questionnaires from a population of 260 employees. The collected data was analysed using Structural Equation Modeling, path analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. The findings revealed that there is a strong negative correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance. A similar study by [Millicent \(2015\)](#) sought to investigate how performance appraisal influences employee performance in Lake Victoria south water services board in Kenya. The study adopted a correlational case study design. A sample of 56 employees was obtained by saturated sampling. Data from respondents was collected using structured questionnaires while secondary data was obtained through literature review. The results showed that the correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance is negative and significant. Moreover, [Miriti et al. \(2021\)](#) examined the performance appraisal as a strategy to enhance performance of employees in teacher training colleges in Kenya. The study obtained data from 282 employees using semi-structured questionnaires. The results from the linear regression analysis indicated a negative relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

2.3.3 Studies showing zero and statistically insignificant correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance.

A study by [Jansen \(2016\)](#) conducted an investigation on the effect of employee performance appraisal on motivation to perform better in the workplace. The study adopted descriptive research design. Data was obtained from 134 respondents from non-governmental organizations. The results of the study showed an insignificant effect of performance appraisal on the intrinsic motivation of employees to perform better in the workplace ($r = 0.03, p > 0.05$). Another study by [Alvi, Surani & Hirani \(2013\)](#) sought to determine the relationship between employee performance evaluation and job satisfaction. Data from 34 respondents was analyzed using graphs and correlation techniques. The study rejected the null hypothesis that performance evaluation creates significant impact on job satisfaction because the correlation coefficient ($p = 0.251 > 0.05$) was found

to be greater than 0.05. The study concluded that there is no significant impact of performance evaluation on job satisfaction. Performance evaluation does not necessarily lead to higher job performance.

A study by [Nhamo \(2020\)](#) assessed the impact of performance appraisal on performance of small scale enterprises in Zimbabwe. The study utilized ex post facto correlational design and quantitative analysis. A sample of 106 owners of the enterprises took part in the survey using structured questionnaires. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The study established that a statistically insignificant relationship exists between performance appraisal and firm performance ($r = 0.046, p = 0.636$). While this study was conducted at organizational level, it contradicted the findings of the previous studies that found that performance evaluation is positively or negatively correlated with individual and firm performance. On the other hand, [Katavich \(2013\)](#) analysed the relationship between performance appraisal, satisfaction and work performance. Data was obtained data from 118 respondents and utilized descriptive and inferential analysis. The study found no significant association between performance appraisal, employee satisfaction and work performance.

3. The way forward: systematization by meta-analysis technique

This study utilized the meta-analysis to examine previous studies in order to arrive at the conclusion about the assumption of the Goal theory in the context of performance appraisal and employee performance. Meta-analysis is a quantitative analysis that involves examination of data from a number of independent studies of the same subject in order to determine generalizations about the overall trends ([Weichselbaumer & WinterEbmer, 2005](#)). A meta-analysis applies objective statistical methods to determine and systematize the variation that exists in studies that seek to address the same research questions ([Haidich, 2010](#)). This study utilizes the "DR. SEAS" approach to meta-analysis. The "DR. SEAS" is an approach that provides the steps needed for conducting a meta-analysis. The D stands for "Defining the research question"; The R stands for "Reviewing the relevant literature"; the first S stands for "Selecting the appropriate studies"; the E stands for "Extracting data"; the A stands for "Analyzing the data" and the second S stands for "Synthesizing the analyzed data". Many researchers such as [Matysiak & Vignoli \(2006\)](#) and [Talic et al. \(2021\)](#) have used the DR. SEAS approach to conduct meta-analysis in their respective studies.

There are many advantages of using meta-analysis over the standard narrative literature reviews. First, meta-analysis objectively summarizes the existing evidence regarding a specific research issue by providing a more objective statistical appraisal of the evidences ([Neyelof, Fuchs & Moreira, 2012](#)). Because of this, meta-analysis minimizes bias by utilizing a well-defined and precise methodological approach to estimate the effect size of the findings of the studies considered in the analysis. According to [Matysiak & Vignoli \(2006\)](#), meta-analysis helps to explain the wide variation in study results and increases the generalizability of the individual studies. However, like any other data analysis technique, meta-analysis has certain disadvantages. First, meta-analysis is limited to the review of previous quantitative studies. This may lead to inaccurate results especially when the previous studies are very heterogeneous in their designs, analysis, quality and study populations ([Fagard, Staessen & Thijs, 1996](#)). A single poorly done study can risk the entire meta-analysis process. Secondly, meta-analysis is vulnerable to publication bias because researchers tend to publish studies that indicate significant effects and may not take the time to publish negative findings. When a metaanalysis is restricted to positive results, then the validity of the whole analysis is compromised ([Matysiak & Vignoli, 2006](#)). Thirdly, some studies do not report complete findings and statistical assessments that are necessary for meta-analysis.

4. Selection of the studies

In order to sample quality data, this study focused on original and reviewed published empirical studies, written in English language. This is because the author of this paper is not proficient in other languages. Materials such as editorial articles, research proposals, commentary reports from newspapers and general information from the internet and other media were not considered for analysis. The reason for excluding these materials is that, often, they do not provide adequate statistical assessments that are required for meta-analysis. Some of the information in the excluded materials are presented subjectively to meet the interests of the authors. Therefore, the articles used in this study were obtained from Journals with high reputation and had sufficient statistical measures for assessing the variables of the study. Furthermore, the author checked the references

used in each of the papers to ensure that their literature was obtained from reliable sources. After a systematic review of the articles, the researcher found 63 articles that sought to examine the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Amongst the articles, only the ones that provided adequate information needed to evaluate the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance were included. At the end of the selection process, the author came up with 27 articles that had the complete information needed for meta-analysis. The researcher proceeded to the next step of coding and extraction of datasets

5. Coding and data extraction

5.1 Identification of Performance Outcomes

The coding of the 27 studies that measured the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance resulted in identification of three performance outcomes (motivation, commitment and goal-achievement). Table 1 below shows the outcome aspects and average weighted reliability (Cronbach’s alpha, α) across the samples.

Table1: Outcomes obtained from coding, aspects of the outcomes average weighted reliability across all the samples.

Performance outcomes	Aspects	Average α
Motivation	Cooperativeness, adherence to controls, loyalty,	.83
	supportiveness and persistence.	.80
Commitment	Task involvement,	.77
	interpersonal engagement, enthusiasm and focused effort.	
Goal-achievement	Quality output, efficiency, timely output, creativity and increased productivity.	

Source: Author’s compilation

5.2 Heterogeneity of the studies

This study utilized QWithin statistic to investigate the heterogeneity of studies. The significant values of QWithin rejected the null hypothesis that the studies are homogeneous. Therefore, significant QWithin values indicated that the studies are heterogeneous. Moreover, the I2 statistic was used to show the percentage of heterogeneity of the studies. Heterogeneity increases with increase in I2. For instance, zero percent indicate no heterogeneity, 50% indicate moderate percentage of heterogeneity and 75% indicate high heterogeneity (Karina et al., 2017; Higgins, Thompson, Deeks, & Altman, 2003).

5.3 Identification of moderators of performance appraisal and employee performance

This study explored the potential moderators of the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. After the review of the existing studies, the researcher considered the possibility that the sector where a study is conducted has a moderating on the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. For instance, a number of studies that were conducted in public organizations showed negative correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance (Attipoe, Agordzo & Seddoh, 2021) while most of the studies conducted in the private sector showed a positive correlation between performance appraisal and employee performance (Ayomikum, 2017; Kumari, 2015). The study also identified study design as a potential moderator between performance appraisal and employee performance. For instance, some of the studies that utilized nonprobability sampling indicated a negative relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance (Naseed et al., 2019) while many studies that used probability sampling found a positive correlation between the two variables. Moreover, a greater percentage of the studies that used longitudinal samples registered negative correlations between performance appraisal and employee performance than the studies that used cross-sectional samples. The other potential moderator is the organizational size. Based on the existing studies, studies that were conducted in small and medium sized enterprises are more likely to find statistically insignificant relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance than the studies that were conducted in larger, established organizations. In this study, the effects of the moderators was investigated using Hedges and Olkin (1985).

According to the test, the presence of moderating factor is indicated by a statistically significant QBetween. Different significant values of QBetween suggests different strengths of association between performance appraisal and employee performance when the moderating variables are included in the analysis.

6. Results

6.1 Overall size effect results

The first objective of this study was to examine how performance appraisal relates to the indicators of employee performance. Table 2 below summarizes the overall meta-analytic results for the weighted average relationships between performance appraisal and the five aspects of employee performance, as estimated with a random effects model.

Table 2: Overall size effects

Performance outcomes	K	N	r	95% CI	80%CV	Qwithin	I ²
Motivation outcome	23	3057	.21	.19 - .23	.04 - .33	1574.22***	89.56
Commitment outcome	21	5544	.15	.13 - .17	.09 - .19	2674.91***	90.22
Goal-achievement outcome	24	4840	.19	.14 - .24	.18 - .20	2153.71***	94.35

Note: k = number of studies analysed; N = total number of participants for all the studies analysed; mean r = Mean weighted correlation coefficient; 95% CI = lower and upper limits of 95% confidence interval; 80% PI = lower and upper limits of 80% prediction interval; QWithin = Chi-square test of heterogeneity within groups; I2 = Percentage heterogeneity. ***p < .001
Source: Literature review, 2025

Performance appraisal was found to be positively related with motivation with a mean correlation of $r = .21$ (95% CI = .19 - .23). The Q statistic for motivation indicated a significant heterogeneity for the relationship between performance appraisal and motivation (Qwithin= 1574.22; $p < .001$; I2 = 89.56). Similarly, the performance appraisal was found to be positively related with commitment with a mean correlation of $r = .15$ (95% CI = .13 - .17). The Q statistic for commitment indicated significant heterogeneity for the relationship between performance appraisal and commitment (Qwithin= 2674.91; $p < .001$; I2 = 90.22). Lastly, performance appraisal was found to be positively related with goal-achievement with a mean correlation of $r = .19$ (95% CI = .14 - .24). The Q statistic for goal-achievement indicated significant heterogeneity for the relationship between performance appraisal and goal-achievement (Qwithin= 2153.71; $p < .001$; I2 = 94.35).

In all the cases, the weighted mean correlations indicated a positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance indicators. The relationship between appraisal and the performance indicators is statistically significant. This study provides support to the previous studies that found that performance appraisal is positively correlated with employee performance. The findings support the assumption of the Goal theory that setting and appraisal of goals correlate positively with performance of employees.

Fig. 3: The Goal theory Framework

Source: Author’s compilation

In addition, in all cases, a considerable high heterogeneity was registered. This is not surprising because the variation results from the differences and peculiarities of the examined studies in terms of the samples used, instruments used, methods applied and analysis employed. Furthermore, the values of 80% CVs were large and included zero, the Q statistic indicated

significant heterogeneity in all the relationships and the proportions of variation were above 60%. These findings indicated that the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance is moderated by other factors. It was important to identify the moderating factors because the Goal theory does not indicate how other variables moderate the relationship between appraisal and employee performance.

6.2 Moderating role of the sector where the study is conducted

The second aim of this study was to find out whether the sector where the study has been conducted as a potential moderator in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Table 3 below presents the findings of the two sectors (public and private) where the examined studies were conducted.

Table 3: Moderation effect of the sector where a study is conducted

Outcomes	K	N	r	95% CI	80%CV	Qwithin	QBetween	I ²
Motivation								
Public sector	8	1223	.19	.12 - .16	-.18-.31	546.30***	102.61***	90.13
Private sector	17	1466	.23	.17 - .29	.02 -.29	601.32***	88.23***	92.11
Commitment								
Public sector	7	447	.15	.11 - .19	.04-.12	412.15***	63.55***	88.21
Private sector	13	1301	.11	.07 - .15	.01 -.17	456.89***	51.88***	91.24
Goal-achievement								
Public sector	10	856	.29	.21 - .37	.13 -.41	422.97***	11.85***	94.77
Private sector	11	1258	.36	.33 - .39	.03 -.39	413.57***	39.77***	90.01

Note: k = number of studies analysed; N = total number of participants for all the studies analysed; mean r = Mean weighted correlation coefficient; 95% CI = lower and upper limits of 95% confidence interval; 80% PI = lower and upper limits of 80% prediction interval; QWithin = Chi-square test of heterogeneity within groups; QBetween = Chi-square test of heterogeneity between groups; I² = Percentage heterogeneity. ***p < .001

Source: Author, 2025

As concerns the sector where a study was conducted, tests for differences between public and private sectors was done for motivation, commitment and goal-achievement. Other performance outcomes were not included because they were not sufficiently provided by the studies that were conducted in the public sector. The values of correlation and Q statistics were examined to identify any differences in the associations between performance appraisal and employee performance in each sector. Interestingly, in all the three performance indicators, this study did not find significant differences between the sectors where the studies were carried out. For motivation, the correlation in the public sector was r = 0.19 with a non-zero confidence interval of (95%CI=.12 - .16) while in the private sector the correlation was found to be r = 0.23 and a non-zero confidence interval of (95%CI=.17 - .29). Similarly, for commitment outcome, both the public

and private sectors showed a positive association with r = .15 (95%CI = .11 - .19) for public sector and r = .11 (95%CI = .07 - .15) for the private sector. For the case of goal achievement, the public sector had a correlation of r = .29 (95%CI = .21 - .27) and the private sector r = .39 (95%CI = .33 - .39). These results reveal that public and private institutions have common characteristics as regards the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

6.3 Moderating role of organizational size

The third aim of this study was to investigate the organizational size as a potential moderator in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Table 4 presents the findings of the organizations (small vs large) for the studies that were examined.

Table 4: Moderating effect of organizational size

Outcomes	K	N	r	95% CI	80%CV	Qwithin	QBetween	I ²
Motivation								
Small organizations	13	1177	.22	.18 - .26	.02 - .29	331.94***	96.52***	93.21
Large organizations	10	1661	.13	.05 - .21	.15 - .30	405.32***	63.52***	94.17
Commitment								
Small organizations	14	1333	.37	.21 - .53	.24 - .41	397.85***	41.29***	90.67
Large organizations	13	986	.15	.14 - .16	.13 - .17	241.22***	80.51***	93.54
Goal-achievement								
Small organizations	11	1802	.41	.31 - .51	.16 - .25	456.71***	31.66***	91.12
Large organizations	17	1956	.36	.32 - .40	.22 - .34	509.87***	50.99***	90.87

Note: k = number of studies analysed; N = total number of participants for all the studies analysed; mean r = Mean weighted correlation coefficient; 95% CI = lower and upper limits of 95% confidence interval; 80% PI = lower and upper limits of 80% prediction interval; QWithin = Chi-square test of heterogeneity; I² = Percentage heterogeneity. ***p < .001

Source: Author, 2025

With regard to the motivation outcome, there was a slight difference in the magnitudes of the average weighted correlation coefficient. The small organizations (r = .22, 95% CI = .18-.28) reported significantly stronger associations between performance appraisal and employee performance. The large organizations (r = .13, 95% CI = .05 - .21) reported a weaker association between performance appraisal and employee performance. Similarly, the relationship between the commitment outcome and performance appraisal was found to be different in the large and small organizations. The small organizations reported a significantly stronger associations (r = .37, 95% CI = .21 - .53) than the public institutions (r = .15, 95% CI = .14 - .16). However, both the public (r = .37, 95% CI = .21 - .53) and private institutions (r = .37, 95% CI = .21 - .53) did not indicate significant differences

in the relationship between performance appraisal and goal achievement. The results indicate a partial moderating effect of organizational size of appraisal-performance relationship.

6.4 Moderating role of sampling technique

The fourth aim of this study was to investigate sampling technique as a potential moderator in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Table 5 below presents the findings of the sampling technique (probability sampling vs nonprobability sampling) while Table 5 for the studies that were examined. Only the studies that indicated the sampling procedure were considered for analysis of the moderating effect.

Table 5: moderating effect of sampling technique

Outcomes	K	N	r	95% CI	80%CV	Qwithin	QBetwee	I ²
Motivation								
Probability sampling	15	1023	.33	.24-.42	.01-.19	340.14***	38.92***	94.44
Non-probability sampling	6	827	.19	.12-.26	-.26-.37	202.22***	40.12***	90.66
Commitment								
Probability sampling	16	2456	.29	.23-.46	.14-.27	379.99***	62.31***	88.55
Non-probability sampling	6	1922	.21	.13-.29	.06-.38	211.62***	56.24***	91.87
Goal-achievement								
Probability sampling	19	1223	.37	.29-.45	.11-.32	415.97***	67.99***	91.11
Non-probability sampling	4	804	.31	.27-.45	.02-.24	38.26***	4.88***	93.77

Note: k = number of studies analysed; N = total number of participants for all the studies analysed; mean r = Mean weighted correlation coefficient; 95% CI = lower and upper limits of 95% confidence interval; 80%PI = lower and upper limits of 80% prediction interval; QWithin = Chi-square test of heterogeneity; I² = Percentage heterogeneity. ***p < .001

Source: Author, 2025

The results in Table 5 indicated that correlational differences exist when probability and non-probability sampling techniques are used to assess the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. The results of studies that used probability sampling indicated a stronger average correlation coefficient of r = .33 and a 95% confidence level between .24 - .42. The correlation result for studies that used nonprobability sampling indicated a weaker correlation of r = .19 and a 95% confidence level between .12 - .26. Regarding commitment, this study revealed a similar trend. The studies that used probability sampling reported a stronger association (r = .29; 95%CI = .23 - .46) than those that used non-probability sampling (r = .13; 95%CI = .13 - .29). The same is for goal-achievement outcome which indicated a stronger association (r = .37; 95%CI = .29 - .45) than the studies that used non-probability sampling (r =

.31; 95%CI = .27 - .45). These results reveal that the type of sampling could result in variations in the appraisal and employee performance.

6.5 Moderating role of sample type

The fifth aim of this study was to investigate how the sample size selected by the existing studies moderate the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Table 6 below presents the findings of the sample type (cross-sectional vs longitudinal) for the studies that were examined. The moderating effect of sample type attracted the attention of this study because researchers have argued that the studies that use cross-sectional samples tend to report stronger associations between study variables. This assumption has not been analysed for performance appraisal and employee performance.

Table 6: moderating effect of sample type

Outcomes	K	N	R	95% CI	80%CV	Qwithin	QBetween	I ²
Motivation								
Cross-sectional	17	1733	.19	.05-.33	.23-.43	259.81***	49.12***	94.34
Longitudinal	3	423	-.09	-.12-.06	.01-.18	54.13***	15.24***	90.51
Commitment								
Cross-sectional	19	1562	.29	.21-.37	.15-.37	34.97***	39.18***	90.83
Longitudinal	3	423	.10	.06-.14	.11-.14	58.61***	22.23***	91.62
Goal-achievement								
Cross-sectional	20	2498	.28	.18-.38	.24-.36	381.69***	59.87***	93.58
Longitudinal	3	423	.09	.01-.17	.09-.12	56.74***	17.67***	91.33

Note: k = number of studies analysed; N = total number of participants for all the studies analysed; mean r = Mean weighted correlation coefficient; 95% CI = lower and upper limits of 95% confidence interval; 80%PI = lower and upper limits of 80% prediction interval; QWithin = Chi-square test of heterogeneity; I² = Percentage heterogeneity. ***p < .001

Source: Author, 2025

The results in Table 6 indicate significant variations in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance when different types of samples are used in a study. For motivation, cross-sectional samples reported a stronger correlation (r = .19, 95%CI = .05 - .33). The longitudinal samples, however, reported a weak negative correlational association of (r = -.09, 95%CI = -.12 - .06). Similarly, in the commitment outcome, the cross-sectional samples reported a stronger correlation (r = .29, 95%CI = .21 - .37) than the longitudinal samples (r = .10, 95%CI = .06 - .14). For the case of goal achievement, the cross-sectional samples reported a correlation of (r = .28, 95%CI = .18 - .38). The correlation was found to be weaker for longitudinal samples (r = .09, 95%CI = .01 - .17).

7. Discussion

This study employed meta-analysis technique to systematize the existing literature on the assumption of the Goal theory with regard to the nature, strength and direction of the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Specifically, the study examined the association between performance appraisal and the three employee

performance outcomes of motivation, commitment and goal-achievement. The study also looked at the potential factors that could moderate the

relationship between the performance appraisal and employee performance. The moderators included the sector where the primary study was conducted (public and private), the organizational size (large and small, the sampling technique (probability and non-probability and the sample type (cross-sectional and longitudinal). The moderators were examined to find out if they could be contributing to the varied findings by existing studies on the assumption of the Goal theory as regards the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

7.1 Performance appraisal and employee performance

The first aim of this study was to examine how performance appraisal relates with employee performance. The average weighted correlation coefficients between performance appraisal and the outcomes of employee performance revealed a consistent trend that performance appraisal in positively correlated with employee performance. The three performance outcomes: motivation (r= .21, k = 23, N = 3057, 95% CI = .19 - .23, 80%CV = .04 - .33, Qwithin = 1574.22 & I² = 89.56) commitment (r= .15, k = 21, N = 5544, 95% CI = .13- .17, 80%CV = .09 - .19, Qwithin = 2674.22 & I² =

90.22) and goal-achievement ($r = .19$, $k = 24$, $N = 4840$, $95\% \text{ CI} = .14 - .24$, $80\% \text{ CV} = .18 - .20$, $Q_{\text{within}} = 2153.71$ & $I^2 = 94.35$) had positive correlation with performance appraisal. These findings are consistent with the assumption of the Goal theory that posit that setting and appraisal of goals are associated with higher motivation, commitment and task performance. Moreover, several other studies (Chaponda, 2014; Nganga, Wanjiku & Sakwa, 2013; Kumari, 2015); Moraa & Datche, 2019) have found that performance appraisal is positively correlated with employee performance. This study, however, contradicts the findings of the existing studies that predict negative correlation (Ahmad et al., 2014; Rahahleh, Alabaddi & Moflih, 2019, Naseed et al., 2019; Attipoe, Agordzo & Seddo, 2021) and statistically insignificant correlation (Jansen, 2016; Alvi, Surani & Hirani, 2013, Nhamo, 2020) between performance appraisal and employee performance. This confirms that the assumption of the Goal theory holds in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. However, moderating factors (discussed below) can cause variations in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance, which may contradict the assumption of the Goal theory.

7.2 The moderating effects

The second aim of this study was to examine the moderating of sector, organizational size, sampling procedure and sample type on the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Analysis of the moderating factors was necessary and provided additional research mechanisms that explained the variations in the linear relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. In the case of the sector where a study is conducted, it was noted that the relationship between performance appraisal and the employee performance outcomes did not differ in both the public and private sectors. All the correlations were positive ($r = .11 - .36$, $k = 7 - 13$, $N = 447 - 1466$, $95\% \text{ CI} = .07 - .39$, $80\% \text{ CV} = .01 - .41$, $Q_{\text{within}} = 412.15 - 601.32$, $Q_{\text{between}} = 11.85 - 102.61$ & $I^2 = 88.21 - 94.77$). This shows that the effect of performance in organizations has the same effect on employee performance, irrespective of whether the organization is public or private. In the context of organizational size, the association between performance appraisal and employee performance differed in large and small organizations for motivation and commitment outcomes ($r = .11 - .36$, $k = 7 - 13$, $N = 447 - 1466$, $95\% \text{ CI} = .07 - .39$, $80\% \text{ CV} = .01 - .41$, $Q_{\text{within}} = 412.15 - 601.32$, $Q_{\text{between}} = 11.85 - 102.61$ & $I^2 = 88.21 - 94.77$). However for the goal-achievement outcome, there was no significant variation between performance appraisal and employee performance in large and small sectors ($r = .11 - .36$, $k = 7 - 13$, $N = 447 - 1466$, $95\% \text{ CI} = .07 - .39$, $80\% \text{ CV} = .01 - .41$, $Q_{\text{within}} = 412.15 - 601.32$, $Q_{\text{between}} = 11.85 - 102.61$ & $I^2 = 88.21 - 94.77$). The larger correlation coefficients in the small organizations reveal that the impact of performance appraisal on employee performance in large organizations may not be as effective as in small organizations. For the sampling procedure, the probability and non-probability sampling procedures indicated varying correlation between performance appraisal and the three outcomes employee performance ($r = .11 - .36$, $k = 7 - 13$, $N = 447 - 1466$, $95\% \text{ CI} = .07 - .39$, $80\% \text{ CV} = .01 - .41$, $Q_{\text{within}} = 412.15 - 601.32$, $Q_{\text{between}} = 11.85 - 102.61$ & $I^2 = 88.21 - 94.77$). Greater variations ($r = .19 - .39$) were also reported within the non-probability sampling techniques. These differences could arise from the lack of representativeness and response errors that is associated with non-probability sampling techniques. Lastly in the type of sample, cross-sectional samples reported stronger association between performance appraisal and employee performance ($r = .11 - .36$, $k = 7 - 13$, $N = 447 - 1466$, $95\% \text{ CI} = .07 - .39$, $80\% \text{ CV} = .01 - .41$, $Q_{\text{within}} = 412.15 - 601.32$, $Q_{\text{between}} = 11.85 - 102.61$ & $I^2 = 88.21 - 94.77$). Previous studies have reported that cross-sectional studies are more likely to over-report strong associations between study variables due to common method variance (Sverke et al, 2019). However, the positive correlations in both the sample types provide evidence for supporting findings about the positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. The results for moderating factors further indicate that the assumption of the Goal theory may not hold in certain circumstances. It is important for organizations to be cautious when using the Goal theory, by first identifying the factors that could moderate its application. Equally, researchers need to be careful about moderating factors when employing the theoretical framework of the Goal theory in their studies, to avoid presenting inaccurate findings on the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

8. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the size effects, this study concludes that the assumption of the Goal theory holds in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. That is, there is a positive relationship between goal setting, goal (performance) appraisal and employee performance. However, the study concludes that in the presence of moderating conditions, the assumption of the Goal theory may not hold. For example, the study noted that the sector (public and private) where a study is conducted does not moderate the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. On the other hand, organizational size (large and small) has a partial moderating effect in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. However, both the sampling technique (probability and non-probability) and sample type (cross-sectional and longitudinal) have full moderating effect on the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Again based on the findings, this study proposes a revised Goal theory framework in the context of the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance as follows:

Fig. 3: Revised Goal theory Framework in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance.

Source: Author's compilation

9. Limitations of the study

This study is limited to meta-analysis of the past studies, some of which may have presented inaccurate information about the assumption of the Goal theory in relation to the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Secondly, the study focused on only three performance indicators (motivation, commitment and goal-achievement). Thirdly, the researcher identified only four moderators (sector, organizational size, sampling technique and sample type) in the current study. Fourthly, the researcher did the selection, coding and analysis alone. This may have led to selection and analysis bias. Lastly, this study was focused on correlational relationships and did not investigate the other associations that might exist between performance appraisal and employee performance.

10. Recommendations for future studies

The future studies should explore the assumptions of other theories such as Social Comparison theory, Feedback Intervention theory and Equity theory in the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. The future studies should focus on more performance outcomes and moderators that this study did not discuss. The future studies also need to meta-analyse many studies for better generalizations of the results. The future studies should equally consider using other statistical approaches such as meta-regression and confirmatory factor analyses to identify more associations between performance appraisal and employee performance. To prevent selection and analysis bias, the future studies need to be conducted by more than one researcher.

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References

- Ahmad, D. I., Danish, D. R., Ali, S., Ali, H. F., & Humayon, D. A. (2018). A Comparative Study of Banking Industry Based on Appraisal System, Rewards and Employee Performance. *SEISENSE Journal of Management*, 2(1), 1-11.
- Alvi, M., Surani, M., & Hirani, S. (2013). The Effect of Performance Evaluation on Employee's Job Satisfaction in Pakistan International Airlines Corporation. *Munich Personal RePEc Archive*, Paper No. 46415.
- Ashima, A., & Gour, S. (2013). Techniques of Performance Appraisal-A Review. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 2(3), 617-621.
- Attipoe, W. E., Agordzo, G. K., & Seddoh, M. J. E. (2021). Effect of Performance Appraisal System on Employee Productivity: Selected High Schools, Ho Municipality, Ghana. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 12(2), 1-14.
- Audrey, C.V., & Patrice, R. (2012). Adaptive performance: A new scale to measure individual performance in organizations. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 29(2), 280-293.
- Ayomikun, I. (2017). Effectiveness of performance appraisal system and its effect on employee motivation. *Nile Journal of Business and Economics*, 3(5), 15-39.
- Chaponda, C. (2014). The Effect of Performance Appraisal on Employee Motivation: A Survey of Slum Based Non-Governmental Organizations in Nairobi (Masters thesis). *United States International University: Nairobi*.
- Cintrón, R., & Flaniken, F. (2011). Performance Appraisal: A Supervision or Leadership Tool? *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(17), 29-37.
- Dijk, V., & Schodl, M. (2015). Performance Appraisal and Evaluation. In book: *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 2nd Ed. Oxford: Elsevier.
- Griffin, M. A., Neal, A., & Parker, S. K. (2007). A new model of work-role performance: Positive behaviour in uncertain and interdependent contexts. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50, 327-347.
- Haidich, A. B. (2010). Meta-analysis in medical research. *Hippokratia*, 14(1), 29-37.
- Hedges, V., & Olkin, I. (1985). Statistical Methods in Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Educational Statistics*, 20(1), doi: 10.2307/1164953.
- Iqbal, N., Ahmad, N., Haider, Z., Batool, Y., & Ul-ain, Q. (2013). Impact of performance appraisal on employee's performance involving the moderating role of motivation. *Journal of Business and Management Review*, 34(981), 1-20.
- Jansen, P. (2016). The effect of performance appraisal on the intrinsic motivation of employees: The moderating role of the managers' implicit person theory (Doctoral dissertation). *Tilburg University, Netherlands*.
- Karina, N., Morten, B., Chidiebere, O., Marja, K., Eveliina, S. & Kerstin, I. (2017). Workplace resources to improve both employee well-being and performance: A meta-analysis. *Work & Stress*, 31(2), 101-120.
- Katavich, K. M. (2013). The importance of employee satisfaction with performance appraisal systems (Doctoral dissertation). *Massey University: Albany, New Zealand*.
- Katerina, V., Andrea, S., & Gabriela, K. (2013). Identification of Employee Performance Appraisal Methods in Agricultural Organizations. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 5(2), 20 - 36.
- Kihama, J. W., & Wainaina, L. (2019). Performance appraisal feedback and employee productivity in water and sewerage companies in Kiambu County, Kenya. *International Academic Journal of Human Resource and Business Administration*, 3(5), 376-393.
- Kumari, N. (2015). To Study the Relationship between Performance Appraisal and Employee Performance in Telecom Sector. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 3(1), 1-5.
- Matysiak, A., & Vignoli, D. (2008). Fertility and women's employment: A meta-analysis. *European Journal of Population*, 24(4), 363-384.
- Millicent, O. (2015). Influence of Performance Appraisal on Employee Performance in Lake Victoria South Water Services Board, Kenya (Masters thesis). *Maseno University: Maseno, Kenya*.
- Miriti, J., Kirima, L., Nzivo, M., Thurania, S., & Budambula, N. (2021). Performance appraisal training of employees: A strategy to enhance employees' performance in public teacher training colleges in Kenya. *Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 13(1), 10-22.
- Moraa, A., & Datche, E. (2019). Effect of performance appraisal on employee performance: a case study of national health insurance fund. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 6(2), 424-442.
- Naseeb, S., Saif, N., Khan, M. S., Khan, I. U., & Afaq, Q. (2019). Impact of performance appraisal politics on work outcome: multidimensional role of intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction. *Journal of Management and Research*, 6(1), 1-37.
- Ndago, E. (2018). The relationship between performance appraisal and employee productivity in the state department for correctional services in Kwale County (Masters thesis). *University of Nairobi: Nairobi*.
- Neyeloff, J. L., Fuchs, S. C., & Moreira, L. B. (2012). Meta-analyses and Forest plots using a microsoft excel spreadsheet: step-by-step guide focusing on descriptive data analysis. *BMC research notes*, 5(1), 1-6.
- Nganga, R., Wanjiku, P., N., & Sakwa, M. (2013). The link between performance appraisal and firm performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(9), 46.
- Nhamo, M. (2020). The perceived impact of performance appraisal on the performance of small-to-medium-sized enterprises in Zimbabwe. *Acta Commercii*, 20(1), 1-11.
- Patrick, K. (2017). Performance appraisals and job satisfaction. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 28(5), 750-774.
- Rabindra, K., & Lalatendu. K. (2017). Employee performance at workplace: Conceptual model and empirical validation. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 5(1), 69-85.
- Sopiah, S. (2016). The relationship between performance appraisal and job performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6(6), 104-15.
- Sumaira, A., & Muhammad, B. (2017). Perceived Performance Appraisal Purposefulness Failure and In-Role Performance and Retaliation: Testing Injustice as Mediator in Public Sector of Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 9(31), 57-68.
- Sverke, M., Låstad, L., Hellgren, J., Richter, A., & Näswall, K. (2019). A meta-analysis of job insecurity and employee performance: Testing temporal aspects, rating source, welfare regime, and union density as moderators. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(14), 2536.
- Talic, S., Shah, S., Wild, H., Gasevic, D., Maharaj, A., Ademi, Z., ... & Ilic, D. (2021). Effectiveness of public health measures in reducing the incidence of covid-19, SARS-CoV-2 transmission, and covid-19 mortality: systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ*, 375:doi: 10.1136/bmj-2021-068302.
- Weichselbaumer, D., & Winter-Ebmer, R. (2005). A meta-analysis of the international gender wage gap. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 19(3), 479-511.